

Anemica: A Mobile Application for Non-Invasive Detection of Anemia Using Palm Images

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Abstract— Anemia is a disease that impacts the lives of individuals on a daily basis, consisting of many types and various symptoms including fatigue, shortness of breath, and weakness. For the detection of anemia, the standard practices have been mostly invasive for patients, which include obtaining blood samples. To simplify this procedure, non-invasive procedures have been developed, which mainly consist of the analyses of images of patients' palms, fingernail beds, or conjunctival pallor. In this paper, we propose a mobile application solution for anemia detection, Anemica, which analyzes the palm images of patients using a trained convolutional neural network (CNN) model and returns anemia estimates and hemoglobin ranges based on the results. This is accomplished by analyzing 16 regions of the palm image, including finger landmarks, with each region categorized into one of four groups based on the calculated erythema indices. The erythema index serves as an indicator of the redness of the respective regions. Our solution integrates findings from the literature review and demonstrates substantial potential for enhanced accuracy and marketability.

Keywords— Adam Optimizer, Anemia, Complete Blood Count (CBC), Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Decision Trees, Erythema Index, F1 Score, Hemoglobin (hB), Image Augmentation, Image Classification, k-Nearest Neighbor (kNN), Naïve-Bayes (NB), ReLU Activation, RGB, Softmax Activation, Support Vector Machine (SVM)

I. INTRODUCTION

Anemia is a condition which affects the lives of many individuals ranging among all ages and genders. There are many causes of anemia, such as iron deficiency, vitamin deficiency, inflammation-based anemia, aplastic anemia, bone marrow disease-related anemia, hemolytic anemia, and sickle cell anemia [1]. Furthermore, the symptoms of anemia can include shortness of breath, fatigue, pale or yellowish skin, irregular heartbeat, chest pain, dizziness, and headaches [1]. These symptoms and variations of anemia make the condition an indispensable matter for health. Anemia has a considerable impact on children and pregnant women [2]. Based on this prevalence and significance of anemia-related conditions, it becomes necessary to detect anemia and treat it as soon as possible.

Anemia is usually detected among patients undergoing invasive methods, such as drawing blood samples to obtain parameters including the complete

blood count (CBC) and the shape/size of red blood cells [3]. Further information may also be requested, such as the medications used by patients as well as their weight [3]. This traditional approach can cause difficulties for patients who suffer from anemia, which has sparked research on non-invasive detection methods

Non-invasive detection of anemia comprises of detecting the anemia status of a patient without the need to engage in physical procedures like drawing blood from patients. After conducting a literature review, we have evaluated numerous research papers concerning non-invasive solutions. These papers analyze body parts such as palm images [4], [5], fingernail beds [9], conjunctival pallor [7], and their combined analysis in children [10]. All of them have shown promising results ranging from 92% to 99% detection accuracy; however, the opportunity of creating a full-fledged product for end-users stemming from such research has not yet been properly explored.

In this paper, we demonstrate our project Anemica, which combines the methodology from existing research for non-invasive detection of anemia-related conditions into a mobile application with high prospects for anemia detection and marketability. It uses a trained convolutional neural network (CNN) model to assign 16 landmarks on a palm image to 4 severity categories based on the erythema indices for each, which indicate the redness of a region. Based on the results, it provides anemia estimates and hemoglobin ranges for each severity category obtained, through a fluid and user-friendly interface. Our approach can be further enhanced with more enriched datasets and training, as it currently faces issues with detection accuracy due to dataset limitations.

II. RELATED WORKS

There exists a plethora of research investigating non-invasive methods of anemia detection. Studies in the literature have focused on image-based approaches for the detection of anemia, in which various body parts are analyzed. These include the analysis of palm images [4], [5], conjunctival pallor [7], fingernail beds [9], and their combined analysis in children for iron-deficiency anemia [10], and they have shown promising results regarding detection accuracy and performance.

A. EfficientNet CNN Models with Palm Images

Amrutesh et al. proposed a convolutional neural network (CNN) based approach to categorize hemoglobin levels of patients using their palm images [4]. This approach establishes a machine learning-based solution, where the images are classified as either being anemic or non-anemic. The EfficientNetB0 model with softmax activation and Adam optimizer demonstrated the best results, with a 97.52% accuracy and an F1 score of 97%. Additionally, their paper has tested the entire EfficientNet model family, ranging from B0 to B7, with a consistent accuracy of over 92% achieved for all. However, the same models using linear activation have reported to be underperforming. As per the data obtained, their study showed a promising approach for anemia detection with high detection accuracy.

B. Ensemble Models with Palpable Palm Images

Appiahene et al. utilized palpable palm images obtained from patients in their study [5]. The dataset used for this study consisted of 710 participants' images obtained from various hospitals in Ghana [6]. These images were extracted and converted to RGB percentiles for training. A hybrid model was developed using ensemble learning models, where the stacking ensemble model obtained the highest accuracy of 99.92%, among testing of other ensemble models. Their study utilized various algorithms including Naïve-Bayes (NB), decision trees, k-nearest neighbor(kNN), support vector machine (SVM), and random forest (RF). The random forest approach gave the highest individual accuracy of 99.53% and an F1 score of 99.61%. Moreover, the study combined the random forest model with the Naïve-Bayes algorithm to get an accuracy rate of 99.93% and a 100% rate on all other parameters including the F1 score. Despite the Naïve-Bayes algorithm resulting with less accurate results where the accuracy remained at 78.16%, the combination of the NB and RF models resulted with a near- perfect accuracy for the classification of palm images. Their study demonstrated an accurate approach for classifying anemic and non-anemic palm images.

C. Conjunctival Pallor Analysis with Phone Cameras

Collings et al. focused on the conjunctival pallor images of patients to determine their anemia status [7]. Their study obtained images of patients' palpebral conjunctivae, which is a mucous membrane that covers the inner surface of the lower and upper lids of the eyes [8]. Phone cameras were used in ambient light, and the hemoglobin concentration was obtained by analyzing the pictures using the erythema index of the conjunctiva, which indicates the redness of the region. The conjunctival erythema indices had a sensitivity of 93% for the training set and 57% for the validation set, with specificity values for detecting anemia obtained as 78% and 83%, respectively.

D. Patient-Sourced Fingernail Bed Image Analysis

Mannino et al. approached the non-invasive anemia detection problem through analyzing the fingernail bed images provided by patients [9]. Their study made use of a phone camera for analysis, and solely utilized patient-sourced photos through a mobile application that analyzes hemoglobin levels of fingernail bed photos. The application

detected anemia, where the hemoglobin levels were less than 12.5 g/dL. The accuracy this study obtained was ± 2.4 g/dL, with a sensitivity rate of 97% when compared with complete blood count (CBC) hemoglobin levels. Furthermore, the application achieved a better accuracy of ± 0.92 g/dL when personalized calibration was utilized.

E. Comparative Multiregional Anemia Detection

Asare et al. came up with a machine learning-based approach to determine whether the analysis of conjunctival pallor, palpable palms, or fingernail images provides a more accurate result for detecting anemia in children [10]. They focused on detecting iron-deficiency anemia and applied the Naïve Bayes, SVM, CNN, kNN, and decision tree approaches. The dataset shares the source with [6], and was collected, preprocessed, and then the detection model was developed. The dataset sizes they obtained were equal for all three regions, which also apply to the augmented version. They have achieved promising results, with the CNN model yielding the best outcome with 98.45% accuracy for the conjunctiva, 98.33% accuracy for the fingernails, and 99.12% accuracy for the palpable palms. The F1 scores, precision levels, and recall levels for the CNN model have also been the most promising, followed by the Naïve Bayes, decision tree, kNN, and SVM algorithms.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Project Background and Aims

With Anemica, we set out to develop a mobile application that would be user-friendly and would detect the anemia status of a patient along with hemoglobin estimates based on the anemia status obtained. Despite the existence of relevant literature for non-invasive detection, there currently is an undiscovered opportunity to simplify the anemia detection procedure for patients through the integration of relevant findings within a mobile application designed to be user-friendly and with appealing visuals. We aimed for the application to work on both iOS and Android phones and designed the application in a cross- platform setting for this purpose. Our application currently holds high potential for future improvements and deliverability for end-users. Its design is momentarily focused on the use of patients; however, the app will also contain an interface for doctors, and a structure connecting patients and doctors will be established upon other features depending on the future potential and prospects for our application.

B. Data Collection and Availability

For the data collection procedures of our project, we have faced various limitations regarding the availability of relevant data for our project design. Parts of the structural basis for our design and most of the dataset we were supplied were provided courtesy of Koç University Hospital, thanks to the support of our advisors Prof. Çiğdem Gündüz Demir and Prof. Öznur Özkasap of the Computer Engineering Department of Koç University, as well as Prof. Özlem Yalçın of Koç University School of Medicine. The dataset we have used for our project were provided with their permission.

To further discuss on data availability, it can be stated that there are available options for finding datasets for palm images, which includes the contents of the ensemble model research [5]. The dataset utilized for [5] was obtained from a publicly available dataset containing 4260 images in total and is available for downloading [6]. However, since the dataset is from hospitals in Ghana, it was not suitable for our purposes as our approach also utilizes the RGB values obtained, and we could have obtained skewed results for patients with lighter skin colors. As a result, we consulted the Koç University Hospital to obtain palm image samples of anemic and non-anemic patients.

Fig. 1. Anemic and non-anemic palm image samples with their erythema index percentiles highlighted.

This dataset was categorized into four, depending on the severity of the anemia for each, which we have also used in our project as our main approach. After filtering through images with unsuitable lighting conditions, image quality, and distance, we were left with 51 images for training. Sample images with severity values 1 and 4 with their erythema index distribution percentiles can be observed in Fig 1. The top left image belongs to an anemic patient, and the top right image belongs to a non-anemic patient. The graphs show the distribution of erythema indices of anemic patients with severity categories 1 and 2 on the left, and non-anemic patients with severity categories 3 and 4 on the right, where the distributions are based on an augmented version of the dataset. The boxes represent 50% of the data in their respective groups. The average erythema index of anemic samples is lower compared to the non-anemic samples. The percentiles of the sample anemic and non-anemic images are highlighted with red and blue dots, respectively. Outlier values for the calculated erythema indices are also present at the ends of the graphs.

Including the augmented version, this remaining dataset of 51 images contained images of the same hand in different

angles. When combining these limitations, we have faced certain drawbacks with obtaining accurate results for our project. However, these can be mitigated with enriched datasets and more specialized training approaches. Possible improvements for the study will be discussed in the upcoming sections.

C. Project Design

We have designed our application Anemica as part of three main components, including the frontend system, backend system, and the image processing system. The application currently supports the patient interface where after creating their accounts, patients are able to scan their palms using their own cameras or by selecting an image from their gallery. We also have initiated a doctor interface which is currently in a primitive state. With the doctor interface, we seek to implement features where doctors are able to create new patients in the patient database. We also strive to initiate specialized scanning features where either the doctor or the patient can select specified regions of their hand and scan for selected regions.

Fig. 2. The general flow and interface plan of Anemica.

The current status of our application incorporates most of the structure plans we have established. The overall diagram demonstrating the planned application can be found in Fig. 2. Patients or general users are able to register to the application, scan their hands and get results on their anemia status, hemoglobin estimates, and recommendations based on the results. While not being fully implemented, doctors are currently able to access the results of an existing patient in the patient database. The separation of doctors and patients and the addition of the remaining planned features for the doctor interface are planned for future implementations.

In this paper, we will be focusing on the details and procedures of the image processing part. We have used Python as the main programming language for the image analysis. For the detection of landmarks on the palm, we have used the MediaPipe library offered by Google [11]. We utilized the

Hand Landmarker task for MediaPipe, which has hand landmark detection for still images as one of its features.

Fig. 3. Each landmark on the left hand provided by Media Pipe HandLandmarker [11].

The library detects 21 landmarks on the hand, with 4 on each finger and one for the base of the hand. Each region detected by the Hand Landmarker is displayed in Fig. 3 [11]. To achieve our goal, we reduced the total regions to 16 to accommodate for the palm region better by combining the landmarks 0, 1, 5, 9, 13, and 17 into one polygonal area. As for the rest of the landmarks, we define rectangular regions with the center being the landmark detected for each of those regions. Concerning the case of augmenting the data we have obtained, we utilized TensorFlow, which we conducted due to the existing limitations of the dataset at hand. After these steps, we used the OpenCV library to create and highlight the

mentioned rectangular and polygonal regions and extract the RGB values for each region.

Fig. 4. The layer diagram of our CNN model and anemia result categorization.

The CNN model we have used classifies a given image into one of the four categories from which the model was trained on. The detailed structure of this model is described in Fig. 4. We initially tested the use of a support vector machine (SVM) classifier to categorize the images based on the RGB parameters but did not obtain promising results. As a result, we utilized a CNN model instead. The accuracy results acquired from the CNN model and a comparison between SVM and CNN models can be seen as displayed in the results section.

Our CNN model makes use of a convolutional layer, a pooling layer, and a dense layer, which then outputs the category for the image given. The categories are numbered from 1 to 4, where 1 indicates the highest severity and 4 indicates the lowest. The model maps the three dimensions of RGB into 1 using the parameters of ReLU activation for the

hidden layer and the softmax activation for the output layer. In order to obtain the best classification, our model used the Adam optimizer. This categorization procedure is applied for each of the 16 regions on the palm and achieved through the calculation of the erythema index for each region.

As described in Equation 1, the erythema index E in our system is obtained from the division of the logarithm value of the red channel intensity I_{red} and the green channel intensity I_{green} . This formula was based on the erythema index calculation used to determine the absorption of red and green light by the hemoglobin in scar tissue and healthy skin [12]. However, it is important to note that the conjunctival erythema index calculations in [7] differ slightly from our formula, where the logarithm values of the red and green channels were calculated separately. The accuracy of our model can also be influenced by this difference, which can be validated with further testing.

$$E = 100 \times \log\left(\frac{I_{red}}{I_{green}}\right) \quad (1)$$

The overall output of our model is an array that contains the percentage for each region based on the erythema index, pertaining to the category assigned, along with the category number for each region. We then export this array through our backend system to the frontend to map the categories for each region in order to display anemia probabilities and hemoglobin ranges.

1. FUNCTION calculate_results(indices, loaded_model)
2. SET results to array of 32 zeros
- 3.
4. FOR i FROM 0 TO LENGTH(indices) - 1
5. IF indices[i] is not NaN THEN
- 6.
7. SET X to [[indices[i]]]
8. SET df to DataFrame(X, columns=['E'])
- 9.
10. SET r to loaded_model.predict(df[['E']], verbose=0)
- 11.
12. SET results[i] to 100 * max(r) / sum(r) # Calculate accuracy
13. SET results[i + 16] to index of max(r) # Record the category
14. END IF
15. END FOR
- 16.
17. RETURN results
18. END FUNCTION

Algorithm 1. Calculation function for the image processing system

In the image processing system, the main calculation is carried out within the result calculation function, which is given in Fig. 5. We take the erythema indices and the trained model as parameters, where we load the model from a .h5 file. We use NumPy and Pandas to predict the category for the erythema index for each region. Then, we load the model and find the accuracy percentages as the first 16 elements of the final array, and the category number obtained in the remaining

part of the array. The hemoglobin ranges we return are assigned to each category, where the riskiest category 1 returns a range of 6.5-7.9 g/dL, 2 returns 8.0-9.9 g/dL, 3 returns 10.0-11.9 g/dL, and 4 returns 12+ g/dL.

IV. RESULTS

During the course of our project design, we managed to achieve promising results, although there is significant room for improvement. As per considerable dataset limitations as well as the lack of thorough exploration of other approaches for training due to time constraints, we managed to obtain strained accuracy levels for our model.

Fig. 5. The support vector visualization of RGB parameters for our dataset.

Before training the CNN model, the SVM classifier we used to classify our images obtained a 45% accuracy for the original image set and a 40% accuracy for the augmented set during training. The SVM visualization for the RGB parameters of our dataset can be found in Fig. 6. Consequently, we opted for the CNN model which maps the three RGB dimensions into one using ReLU and softmax activation functions, with the Adam optimizer to obtain better classification results.

This model obtained a 48% accuracy for the training phase, and a 46% accuracy for the testing phase, where relevant regions to corresponding severity categories were assigned. For the CNN approach, we divided the dataset into training and testing sets with a 20% test ratio. We tested our model on the dataset divided into four severity categories. However, our model was not very successful on assigning the images to each of the severity categories, where the output of our tests mainly consisted of predicting the severities of images as 2 or 4. To improve the precision of our model's classification, we have tried different approaches to our training logic, as well as trying out different augmentation approaches. Despite these attempts, the precision of our model has mostly remained the same, especially with category predictions. Due to this outcome, as well as to obtain clearer metrics for our model, we have decided to measure the performance our model with a binary approach. In this approach, we checked if the category predictions of 1 or 2 were matching with anemic images, and if the category predictions of 3 or 4 were matching with non-anemic images. Using this approach, we have obtained an overall detection

accuracy of 70.6%, a recall rate of 41.8%, a precision rate of 63.1%, and an F1 score of 50.3% for our CNN model.

Fig. 6. The correlation chart of the erythema indices of the original dataset for each severity category.

The erythema indices we obtained for each image for our original dataset also show a correlation, with some outliers present. The chart that demonstrates this distribution is given in Fig. 7, where we observe a correlation for the erythema index obtained for each image based on the category they belong. As the categories progress from 1 to 4, the overall erythema indices obtained are increasing. This occurs as the overall redness of the images increase with the reduction of the anemia risk. This chart demonstrates the consistency for our approach using erythema indices of the palms to detect anemia and hemoglobin values.

In addition to our approach for the detection of anemia and hemoglobin values, we have also achieved promising results for the interface and usability of our application. Example screenshots for our application, including the result pages which are connected with our image processing system can be found in the Appendix. Alongside providing a comfortable way for detecting anemia, we have also managed to create a dynamic, appealing, and user-friendly interface to enhance the prospects for our project Anemica. Once a user creates their account and logs in, they are greeted with the main dashboard of our application. In this dashboard, users can see the result of their latest test, informative cards about the causes of anemia and how it can be reduced, and widgets mentioning how to scan and previous results which take the user to the analysis page and the result page, respectively. When the analysis page is launched, the user is greeted with a tour on how to get ready for a scan. Once the tour is completed, the user is prompted with two options consisting of selecting an image from their gallery or taking a new photo. Once an image is selected or a photo is taken, the user can send that photo for analysis.

The image analysis currently takes around 30 seconds to 1 minute to fully complete. When the analysis page is launched, the user is greeted with a tour on how to get ready for a scan. Once the tour is completed, the user is prompted with two options consisting of selecting an image from their gallery or taking a new photo. Once an image is selected or a photo is taken, the user can send that photo for analysis. The image analysis currently takes around 30

seconds to 1 minute to fully complete processing the images and displaying the results, along with the regional highlighted version of the image provided in the results page. Users will be able to see their results in the results page once the analysis is completed, where they can see additional information upon tapping on an existing result. In addition to these pages, we also have a profile page in which users can see their information including their name, age, and gender, with a profile photo section which is currently not functional. From the profile page, users are currently only able to log out of the application and delete their accounts

V. DISCUSSION

A. Comparison

The results obtained within existing literature have mostly provided highly accurate results with the help of the combination of different machine learning algorithms and training approaches. Our model has observed a significantly strained training accuracy level of 48% compared to existing studies, which have mainly achieved training accuracy levels of over 90%.

Our model has suffered from other metrics as well, with a recall rate of 41.8%, a precision rate of 63.1%, and an F1 score of 50.3%, in addition to a more moderate detection accuracy of 70.6%. However, it is important to note that we worked with a very limited dataset consisting of 51 images. With the provision of considerably higher numbers of images or datasets, when accounted for adequate lighting and distance conditions for palm images of anemic and non-anemic patients, we can achieve much better results for our project and model.

B. Limitations and Improvements

As discussed previously, our CNN approach and current anemia detection system faces various limitations. Besides the data limitations, we also faced issues with obtaining images with appropriate lighting conditions and angles. The training set we used to train our model only consisted of palm images, whereas we also provided results based on finger landmarks for a more comprehensive analysis. We used the model trained based on palm images for the finger landmarks, which has also impacted the accuracy of our approach. To account for these shortcomings, our model can be refined with an approach where each of the 16 regions are trained separately, with the help of an enriched dataset. Using pretrained models can also be a viable option for our case, if we are unable to resolve dataset issues. We have also utilized the detection of palm images instead of other regions like the conjunctivae or fingernail beds for the purpose of simplifying the detection procedure for patients and doctors. Also seen in previous pages, there exists a multitude of studies focusing on analyzing palm images for non-invasive anemia detection, which has also been an important parameter in our decision for Anemica.

In addition to improvements for our image processing system, we also plan improvements for the existing functionalities of our application on top of improvements for the user interface, depending on the future prospects of our project. For instance, the full integration of the doctor

interface would be a monumental addition to our application to enhance the patient-doctor interactions on detecting their anemia conditions and treating them in a more comfortable fashion. Feature improvements for privacy concerns including the ability to delete all data for an existing patient as well as the separation of doctor and patient information are also among our reinforced plans to ensure an enhanced product with promising utility.

VI. CONCLUSION

Anemia is a condition which impacts the lives of many individuals regardless of age or gender. In the traditional approach, patients are diagnosed through invasive means that involve drawing blood, which can cause distress for the patients. Consequently, non-invasive detection approaches of anemia conditions have gained monumental importance. With our project Anemica, we combined existing literature of non-invasive detection methodology to come up with a marketable and comfortable anemia detection application using palm images. To provide a broader perspective, we utilized erythema index calculations for finger landmarks in addition to the palm. Despite existing limitations for Anemica, there is significant room for improvement for accuracy. As part of identifying anemia, our application Anemica demonstrates high potential and prospects for becoming a valuable tool for patients and healthcare professionals.

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